

F – 01

An Assessment of distribution of Airborne Microplastic using Epiphytic Crustose Lichens in Surrounding Areas of an Open Dumpsite of a Plastic Crusher Plant at Kanadola, Sri Lanka

B.H.P.H. Peiris*, R.G.U. Jayalal and S.S.R.M.D.H.R. Wijesekara

*Department of Natural Resources, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Sabaragamuwa
University of Sri Lanka, Belihul Oya, Sri Lanka*

**Prameshsheshan95@gmail.com*

Airborne microplastics (AMPs) have gained significant global attention due to their presence in the atmosphere and potential risks to human health and the environment. This study focuses on the assessment of microplastic contamination in the air originating from an open dumpsite of a plastic crusher plant in Kanadola, Sri Lanka. Epiphytic crustose lichen samples were collected from trees using stratified random sampling. The study area was divided into three sampling zones based on the distance from the plastic crusher plant: a proximate zone (n=4, 50 m), an intermediate zone (n=3, 50-100 m), and a distant zone (n=3, 100-200 m). In addition, epiphytic crustose lichen samples (n=3) were collected from an undisturbed forest patch at Kumbalgama, as the background control experiment. The acid-digestion method was employed to release the accumulated microplastics from the lichen thallus. Microscopic analysis and a hot needle test were used for microplastic visual inspection and identification, respectively. The total number of microplastics per 1 g of dry weight of lichen in each sampling zone was statistically analyzed using one way ANOVA and the results revealed a significant difference ($p=0.003$) in AMPs distribution among the sampling zones. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using the Tukey test indicated no significant difference in AMPs distribution between the proximate zone and the intermediate zone, but it significantly differed from the control site. In conclusion, this study highlights substantial plastic pollution in the proximate zone and the intermediate zones of the plastic crusher plant site compared to the forest (control) site. The findings underscore the potential of lichen as a biomonitoring agent for qualitative and quantitative analysis of airborne microplastic pollution.

Keywords: airborne microplastics, biomonitoring, epiphytic crustose lichens, hot needle test, stratified random sampling